

THE USE OF FRP COMPOSITES IN RAIL VEHICLES

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1. INTRODUCTION

Construcciones y Auxiliar de Ferrocarriles, S.A., known as CAF, is the largest company in Spain manufacturing railway equipment.

Created en 1917, it now employs almost 2700 people divided among 3 sites: Zaragoza, Irun and Beasain, where the principal factory and head office are situated. Hundreds of locomotives, train carriages of all types, boogies, spare parts, coming from its workshops are destined for the Spanish market and abroad.

In following its traditional policy of support and development of its basic technology (forge, foundry, boiler-making), CAF remains very aware of the development of new materials and processes which could be used in this activity. By opting for the integration of a composite workshop in order to complete its metal activity, CAF is following a specific approach concerning composites which are more and more employed for overhead and underground railways.

A workshop was created at Irun (Guipuzcoa, Basque Country) in 1987, specially designed for the trasformation of composite materials. CAF manufactures all types of parts for railways (foreparts, desks, seats and interior linings,...) essentially in FRP, by contact molding, simultaneous projection, low presure compression and vacuum molding.

2. RECENT DEVELOPMENTS IN VEHICLES WITH AN IMPORTANT PLASTICS APPLICATION

In recent years the trend towards an extension of the use of plastics has increased, especially in the field of the functional parts. In many areas the material-specific advantages of plastics have been utilized more widely in design, dimensioning and specification, with the increasing use of special, advanced plastics types.

As regards quantities, passenger vehicles are at the forefront, since these form the chief applications, especially in interior fittings. Goods wagons (with the exception of the interior linings of refrigerated wagons) and locomotives (with the exception of the cladding parts) are of especial interest regarding the use of plastics for technical functional components. Of the recent developments for passenger services made by CAF, the following vehicles with a significant plastics applications especially deserve mention:

1. RENFE (Spanish National Railways) Three Series of E 444-5 Electric trainset for long distance passenger service. The foreparts (cabin train ends) are in FRP.
2. METRO MADRID (Madrid Subway). Serie 2000 Electric Train Units. Interior finish of glass fibre reinforced polyester paneling ; M1 grade fireproof. Anti-vandalisin seating.
3. F.C. METROPOLITANO DE BARCELONA (Barcelona Subway).Serie 2000 Electric Trains Units. Interior finish of fire-resistant fiberglass reinforced polyester elements in sides and roof.
4. RENFE. Three Series of UT-446 and one Serie of UT-447 Electric suburban trainset. The foreparts and the interior finish is GRP. Seats, also reinforced polyester, with removable cushiones contact areas.
5. METRO MADRID. Serie 5000 Electric Train Units. Foreparts and interior finish of FRP. Antivandalisin-seating.

3. VEHICLE INTERIOR FITTINGS

As can be recognized from the enumeration of recent developments in vehicles, the trend towards the application of large elements for the interior fittings of passenger vehicles has made large advances. The mouldability and free-formability of fibre-reinforced plastics parts, such as exist in the commercial application of the wet-moulding process for small series and the hot pressing process for medium series production, are fully utilized for vehicles design. Side wall elements and ceiling elements can thus be formed into shapes that correspond to the desired designs. The interior design of the Metro de Madrid car is a typical example (Figure 1). Openings for light fittings or communications installations can be integrated. The further use of GRP for casings of the rails of luggage racks, for partition wall facings and seat claddings produces an individualized room design for rail vehicles (Figure 2)

For large series, for which an element construction and standardization of cladding units is necessary, SMC parts can be used to advantage, which makes paintings of the parts unnecessary and ensures uniform colouring, and, if a suitable coating resin is chosen, also permit scratch-resistant, easy-to-maintain surfaces.

The sanitary compartment of GRP already described have gained complete acceptance as constructional elements in new construction as well as in the modernization of existing passenger vehicles.

Installations elements in interior furnishings are replaced at greater intervals as part of maintenance and must be available in large quantities over longer periods of time.

Whilst upholstery foams were previously exclusively made of PUR flexible foam, with the exception of the above-mentioned integral foam parts, a trend towards using HRCM foams can be seen for the actual seat upholstery. The reasons for this are the increased demands made for the fire behaviour of the seats. Interior linings with textile-laminated mouldings, such as are normal in motor vehicles construction have not yet established themselves because of serious problems of maintenance and cleaning in heavy-duty public rail transport.

4. EXTERIOR CLADDING PARTS

Here, mainly the side aprons or apron flaps under the main girder of railcars deserve mention. They consist of a core composite with facings of FRP and a rigid foam core. A part of this apron is removable to facilitate work of the technical installations behind them (switch boxes, batteries, air conditioning systems).

5. OTHER TECHNICAL FUNCTIONAL PARTS

In the highly diversified park of the rail vehicles, with its many different models of locomotives, railcars, goods wagons and special service vehicles, each tailored to a specific need, there can naturally be found, as with many other large products of a highly technological age -more or less evident- innumerable different technical parts with the functions slipping, frictional sliding, rolling, guiding, limiting, dampening, insulating, etc. Strength, impact resistance, compressibility, wear resistance, resistance to environmental exposure and corrosion, electrical insulation, etc.- these are the demands that are made individually or in combination on the plastics used. Examples for these kinds of parts are:

- insulating house for terminal blocks with special cage clamp springs for electrical wiring of rail vehicles; as housing material, heat stabilized PA 6.6 with electrical insulating properties and high tracking resistance is used
- water tanks in HDPE or GRP.
- PUR integral foams parts of seats have proved themselves now that the fire behaviour in this rigid formulation has been considerably improved.

6. FRP COMPOSITES AND FIRE SAFETY

In last years, the problem of the fire safety has increased in significance for the employment and the selection of plastics in general, and the FRP Composites in particular, for rail. Technical legal provisions for rail vehicles vary from country to country and with the type of vehicles. In addition, operators frequently stipulate that various specifications laid down in conditions of purchase must be met.

Unification of regulations in order to meet the requirements of international rail transports, is important particularly for those countries connected by a rail network. European and Asian railway administrations are represented in the "Union Internationale des Chemins de Fer" (UIC) which is establishing the UIC Code covering regulations, recommendations and uniform conditions of supply for rail vehicles. For the fire safety regulations considered, the standard section of UIC 564 Part 2 were passed in 1991, which regulate the fundamentals, risk classification of vehicles, design requirements for vehicle classification, electrical safety measures and accompanying measures such as fire alarm facilities and fire fighting appliances.

In Spain, guidelines on the design and construction of railway passenger rolling stock relating to fire are given in the Technical Instruction on Fire Protection "Directriz Técnica DT-PCI/5A" of RENFE. The guidelines cover new vehicles and changes to existing vehicles. The methods used to determine fire performance are described in a series of standards issued by the Asociación Española de Normalización y Certificación (AENOR) in 1990, namely UNE 23-102 and 23-721 to 23-730. The fire performance of materials is divided into five classes: M0 to M4. Only the abstract symbols M0 to M4 are now used to characterise the results of fire tests. Terms such as non-flammable, etc. used previously were frequently regarded as properties of the material and often led to incorrect interpretation.

Whilst the current state of development of standardization work and of the regulation is intended essentially to cover only the prevention of a fire by arson and to some extent by technical deficiencies, in the future a widening to include delaying the spread of a fire and the behaviour during a full fire is intended. Further restrictions on the use of plastics could also result from this, as well as an additional requirement for fire safety systems for seals, room enclosures with defined fire resistance, or for coatings.

7. PROBLEMS OF SPECIFICATIONS

For rail transport concerns, but also for the relevant supply industry for rail vehicles and accessory parts, the problem often arises of proper materials specifications for plastics. An optimum solution, namely to determine the minimum materials properties required for the function of the component, e.g. by reference to a material standard with details of properties, is usually not possible for plastics, especially in view of the extensive type specialization. Manufacturers' information and product descriptions can often not be used, however, because they also mean a restriction to a product of a particular company and the competition in the contract award would be unnecessarily limited.

If the required catalogue of properties cannot be guaranteed because of a lack of adequate experience, service tests or short-term tests are required before the first application of new company products for safety-critical or economically relevant applications and company products selected by approval on the basis of a first sample.

It is anticipated that after long operating experience with several materials, it will be possible to summarize the requirements catalogues into requirements groups on the basis of the performance properties, with subsequent standardization according to applications. Additional supply agreements, especially for quality testing will be stipulated by the Spanish National Railways in a technical terms of delivery.

Figure 1. METRO DE MADRID Serie 2000. Interior design

Figure 2. RENFE. UT-447. Driving desk

Figure 3. METRO DE MADRID. Serie 5000. External view

Figure 4. RENFE. UT-446. External view